

Fig 1. Spectrum fit with the 1D-RCTE ScCHIMERA grid using PyMultiNest. The top panel shows planet flux/stellar flux, while the bottom shows planet brightness temperature. One and two standard deviation confidence intervals are shown in blue, and NIRISS data is shown in grey.

Fig 2. Pressure-temperature profiles from grid points that fall within the Bayesian posterior distributions of parameter estimations (see Fig 3).

Fig 3. Parameter estimations from the 1D-RCTE grid retrieval. We plot Bayesian posterior distributions and present values for the best fit \pm one standard deviation.

Fig 4. Spectra showing the impact of each parameter. All spectra are the best-fit values (redistribution factor $f=1.69$, $C/O=0.03$, $[M/H]=-0.08$) apart from a specified change.